

Research Data Canada

Why does Canada need Research Data Canada?

Government departments, higher education institutions and other publicly-funded research organizations produce huge volumes of research data that hold enormous potential for discovery and innovation. This data can be re-purposed and re-used in a multitude of ways by researchers, industry, policy makers, and civil society, effectively saving millions of research dollars, and countless work hours. However, in order for this data to be reused, proper long-term preservation and access is crucial. As this data is distributed across a range of institutions, no single institution can address the challenges of managing this data alone. That's where Research Data Canada comes in.

What is Research Data Canada?

Research Data Canada (RDC) is a stakeholder-driven and supported organization dedicated to maximizing the value of research data in Canada through better research data management practices. RDC was established in 2011, and CANARIE has supported its activities since 2014. RDC continues to play an essential role in mapping Canada's data landscape.

Several stakeholder groups across Canada are now engaged in developing and delivering a range of research data management services and resources. RDC bring together these key stakeholders to:

- > facilitate communications and partnerships,
- > promote education and training, and
- > develop strategy for addressing gaps in our research data management ecosystem.

RDC provides a focal point for communication, providing a single point of contact for Canada in international initiatives while ensuring effective engagement across the stakeholder community.

What is Research Data Management?

An effective research data management framework:

- > preserves and increases access to research data, thereby facilitating greater discovery and the ability to verify research results;
- > increases opportunities for collaboration and innovation, leading to higher impacts of research, both for researchers and society at large;
- > facilitates accessibility to all research results, negative and positive; and
- > makes data available using international norms and standards, increasing the use and exchange of research across disciplines and in the development of more robust policy.

What benefits does Research Data Canada provide Canadians?

Research Data Canada:

- > provides Canadians with a vision and representation for all stakeholders (publicly-funded researchers and organizations that fund them) in the research community;
- > promotes best practices in research data management across Canada, allowing increased access to research data;
- > represents the interests of the Canadian research community and facilitates collaboration with institutional, regional, national, and international efforts, services, and resources; and
- > facilitates a culture of innovation and discovery through promotion of open sharing of research data.

These efforts are a reflection of Research Data Canada's interest in the full breadth of the research data lifecycle, which is represented below by a diagram created by the Digital Curation Centre¹.

A National Collaboration

RDC's initiatives are made possible through the participation of the broader research data management community in Canada, reflected in the activities of the Steering Committee and its four sub-Committees: Standards and Interoperability; Infrastructure; Policy; Communications, Outreach and Education.

To participate in and contribute to the development of a robust Canadian research data management ecosystem, please contact us:

info@rdc-drc.ca

¹ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/meeting-the-requirements-of-the-EP SRC-research-data-policy>